

DIYR - DIY-Redefined, exploring the innovative potential of designing DIY electronics

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Abstract

In times of multiple crisis, embracing alternative materials, products, and manufacturing systems is indispensable together with a change in our relation to them. Constant technological development alongside surging consumer demand for the new leads to the multi-faceted problem of ever-increasing production and waste of electronic goods. Starting from the principles of openness, democratization of technology, and distributed manufacturing, the design-driven research project DIYR (Do-It-Yourself Redefined) focuses on common electronic appliance typologies designed to be self-produced. It aims at enabling proDusers (producer/ user) to actively explore, gradually understand, produce, and adapt a growing range of unique electronic appliances. Thus, giving rise to a more sustainable, responsible, and holistic ecosystem of electronic products, facilitating knowledge and technology transfer together with essential circular values. Likewise, the project collaborates with Fab Labs, serving as a new communication tool and an instrument to highlight its capacities, amplify and gain the engagement of existing and new users. This paper addresses DIYR as an example of a design-led project merging the essence of the Maker culture and the principles of DIY by enriching them with the main characteristics of the design expertise: the capability of decreasing complexity and optimizing functionality ranging from formal aesthetics to aesthetics in interaction.

Keywords

DIY(Do-It-Yourself), electronics, design-driven innovation, open design, sustainability

1 Introduction

While incremental growth of electronic goods follows unsustainable production, and use patterns dictated by the market economy, the democratization of technology and growing awareness, together with open design and distributed manufacturing, aim to reverse this tendency, bringing transparency to the 'black boxes' and shift the power back to a well-informed consumer. The DIYR research project is rooted in those principles and strives to formulate answers to the following questions: in what ways could design-driven artefacts serve as sustainable catalysts for the DIY, maker world, and industry? As the form-follows-function dogma on all its positive values hardly exists in electronic artefacts, what are possible alternatives 'DIYR electronics' could offer in changing that? Could design-driven innovation give new sense/s to distributed manufacturing and Fab Labs as viable local production or production-support hubs?

By collaborating with Fab Labs, the project aims at providing them with valuable ways in which they could better demonstrate their capabilities, amplify engagement with their existing users and attract new user groups. It also caters for valuable knowledge and value transfer, enabling a deeper understanding of electronics, design, and production, coinciding with sustainability and circular values.

This paper addresses the DIYR project as an example of design-led research intersecting with the maker world, offering new possibilities of fusing together aesthetics of form, function, environment, production, use, and user. It merges the essence of the Maker culture and the principles of DIY and enriches them with characteristic design values: a holistic perspective over the complete project, decreasing complexity, optimizing functionality while highlighting both formal aesthetics as well as the aesthetics of interaction. By doing so, it gives rise to new typologies and narrations of products within a shared, open, and transparent system. Besides, this project delivers important educational values for a more conscious, responsible, and proactive attitude towards our material world and the environment. These values are strengthened by making recipes of products as “commons” that can be fabricated by anyone, anywhere, and in the same way, be repaired and sustained for a longer period.

2 Designing DIY

2.1 Basic logic and development of DIY

“Openness” is a key concept in coping with the societal or environmental complex problems that we are facing in the last decades (van Abel, et al. 2011). Thus, designing in an environmentally conscious manner requires a fundamentally different attitude – one that is no longer aligned with linear growth and constant consumption but proposes alternative and sustainable solutions in applying this openness on a systemic level. Do-It-yourself – a concept at the heart of open design – thrives on personal initiative, conscious handling, freedom of making, and openness.

How is DIY defined?

The term 'DIY' is a formula: Every time you 'do' a certain 'it' by 'yourself', it is a DIY. In the past, almost everything was done by 'ourselves'. Therefore, there was no special term for it. The term DIY is a recent one, and in common use since the 1950s' (Science Museum, 2020). DIY could be now seen as bringing back possibilities that we had but seem to have lost and are now being re-discovered. Commonly seen, DIY is a method of building, modifying, or repairing things without the direct aid of experts or professionals.

'DO' means any action

'IT' could be practically anything

'YOURSELF' is anyone

Figure 1: DIY concept by Cohen

Hence, the basic logic of Do-It-Yourself can be circumscribed as follows: Every 'DO' begins with a need or a will. Thus, DIY is the act of transforming a 'promise' into reality, shifting from an intangible and disembodied form of desire to a tangible artefact and an embodied experience that transforms not only

the artefact but also the “self” in the process. As illustrated in Fig.1, depending on the experience of DOing, the impact on the SELF is either positive or negative. The 'SELF' is evolving with the DOing and objects that are closer to our 'SELF' affect it in a powerful way. The approach of DIY can be extended to DIT (Do-It-Together) and thus, alters from a self-oriented activity to a collective one.

Either the approach of Do-It-Yourself or the concept of Do-It-Together, sustainably form and affect the producers and consumers – the so-called “prosumers” (Toffler, 1980, 283), outlining the consumers being producers for their consumption (Xie, et al. 2008). A concept which, according to Toffler, has already existed for centuries, although it contradicts classical marketing strategies of today where the consumer merely represents a passive responder (ibid.).

Whilst there exist already different DIY products and concepts in the market, it is most commonly a mere solution for lowering costs. Resulting in products with an inferior value to their non-DIY equivalents as reflected in the ‘knock-down’ products of IKEA. As such, the DIY products and their perception prevail to be remote from technological advancement and innovation at large.

DIY is on the rise and its comeback echoes through different channels. One of the driving factors for it could be seen in the democratization and accessibility of technology together with the integration of craft and digital fabrication techniques with vast and easily accessible corresponding knowledge mostly through online platforms and physical spaces-hubs like Fab Labs and makerspaces. Especially in times of the COVID-19 pandemic, DIY is booming due to changing needs, use of (“free”) time, and rising convenience in society (Maida, 2020), which can be observed as well by the stock value growth of America's largest DIY chains (Gray, 2020). Although this growth still refers to the more traditional forms of DIY and “home improvement” of sorts, it highlights the potential and needs for more advanced and innovative evolutions of DIY.

2.2 Design & DIY

Models of a generative or open-source design challenge the current role of design, fostering new production models to emerge and grow (Maffei & Bianchini, 2016). “The designer of the future has to become a (...) meta-designer, (...) shaping a design space in which unskilled users can access user-friendly environments in which they can design their own objects” (de Mul, 2011, 34). In the 70s’ designers such as Enzo Mari, Victor Papanek, or Ken Isaacs, brought initial ideas of DIY furniture by creating concepts of self-constructible systems offering an encounter area between designers and users meant to counteract formalism and to democratize both, design and production. In the same vein, the Social Furniture project by EOOS aims to create furniture designs for a new togetherness as alternative models to the way we live and work in today's society (EOOS, et al. 2016). In these examples, the common thread is that the designer does not only bring a technical innovation but a social innovation that resonates with society's real needs.

With the development and democratization of digital technologies such as the Arduino platform, the DIY movement has gained a different dimension embracing also technological devices. Constant innovations and improvements in technology as well as the simplified access to digital media facilitated non-experts to tinker with technology. This fostered the start of the maker culture - a constructivist approach of learning-through-doing (Mauroner, 2017). Personal fabrication centers have become spaces offering facilities and resources for working, along with the supportive expertise of Makers (Heyer, 2014). These centers not only give services for their members to simply construct things but also, they become hubs for innovative projects that are critically engaged with environmental and societal issues (Smart Citizen, 2021). Yet observing what is often produced in some digital production centers leads to critically acknowledging the gap between innovative possibilities and potential and the reality of environmentally and conceptually questionable artefacts, highlighting a lack in qualitative orientation and genuine content. To leverage this potential of Fab Labs, a design-driven approach can bring “meaning making” (Verganti, 2009) into the actual “making” process.

With its focus on DIY electronics through a design-driven approach, the DIYR project draws inspiration from relevant design-led projects dealing with DIY products containing electronic components. ‘Hacking Households’ by designer Jesse Howard tackles neighboring challenges through which he generated a new aesthetic while giving DIY instructions to follow the process of de/ re-constructing electronic households,

such as a mixer and a fan. Another example is the project Superlocal by Andrea de Chirico, focusing on local resources, in the form of materials and labor, and the creation of a local network of craftsmen and Fab Labs, intending to connect the consumer with the product's narrative (De Chirico, 2015). Another valuable reference is OpenStructures (OS), an open modular construction system that promotes circular material flows and facilitates reuse and repair. (OpenStructures, 2019). The approach of the community-driven design project 'Precious Plastic' is based on custom-made machines to recycle and produce a growing catalog of plastic products out of plastic trash (Precious Plastic, 2000). The most unique aspect of this large-scale project is the extensive network and growing community it engages through a distinctive and comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy.

2.3 Beyond the planned obsolescence

Openness has the potential to counteract the unsustainable consumption boosting methods of industry, such as the strategy of planned obsolescence initially introduced by the US automobile market. Since the planning and design of the end-of-life product (EOL product) constitutes an integral part of the development process in companies, the term planned obsolescence can be used to refer to the (artificial) aging of products (Prakash, et al. 2016). Although it has (obviously) not been confirmed that companies intentionally shorten the service life of products to boost consumption, the problematic conjuncture of (planned) obsolescence is particularly acute nowadays with electronic appliances.

According to the annual Global E-Waste Monitor, in 2019 the amount of e-waste rose to nearly 54 million tons (Berthold, 2021). More sustainable, alternative electrical products are scarce. A few examples of such alternatives are Fairphone or Shiftphone, the fair computer mouse from Nager IT, or the charging cables from Recable (ibid.). Shifting from closed boxes to transparency, the DIY electronics principle can help going beyond the planned obsolescence towards a system of products in which new values for longevity are embedded through the engagement of the user in making and maintaining processes.

3 DIYR

DIYR is a design research project that develops new recipes for self-produced electronic products. It seeks to expand and enrich both the notion of DIY and the DIY world/s as well as the world of electronics. In the initial part of this project some products - such as Bluetooth speakers, and a family of lamps were designed and developed by combining digital fabrication methods with commonly available local materials and components together with a wide scope of online available electronic components. A red thread running through the complete design process is a revised modernistic principle - form follows function, production, and longevity. While the DIYR products offer easy-to-follow assembly instructions and the possibility to produce them by anyone and anywhere, the direct production and the exclusion of any aspect which is not essential for the proDuser brings new formal and typological possibilities. New interaction modalities and wide personalization possibilities (Fig.2, Bluetooth loudspeaker) are enhancing user experience, bringing with it an emotional and personal attachment to the product. In the following stage of the project, the main objective is to bring the DIYR concept and its design-driven approach into a more extensive discourse within the Fab Lab community to challenge it with a higher amount of proDusers and optimize the project accordingly.

3.1 The aim of DIYR

Questioning current conventions of industrial production, the redefined approach of Do-It-Yourself offers an alternative concept that empowers users and incorporates educational values. Likewise, new technological achievements offer unprecedented opportunities to be applied and used practically by anyone. However, these are rarely noticed. A wide gap in access, know-how, or own initiative prevents a wide potential crowd from working with technology and electronics in particular. Also, those that are proficient in working with electronics struggle to orientate in the vast scope of components, technologies, suppliers, and availability.

Figure 2: DIYR - Bluetooth loudspeaker (construction and personalization)

As a result, many technological innovations and possibilities are unseen or underexplored, which is another aspect where the DIYR project aims to intervene. Through easy-to-follow step-by-step instructions, the project is offering access to the world of electronic appliances which are otherwise mass-produced. Enabling one to actively explore, gradually understand, adapt, produce, and use it in a participatory aware manner. Acknowledging that a growing understanding will lead to more conscious and responsible interaction with electronic goods and beyond.

Furthermore, the project is proposing a way to counter the tendency of intransparent and obsolete product development by elevating user involvement and understanding, resulting in clearer expectations and acceptance as it was produced by oneself. DIYR additionally aims at raising awareness for the so-called 'second life' recycling of batteries. In 2020 the global demand for batteries was around 282.000.000 Kilowatt and it is expected to increase by a factor of ten, reaching 2030. This massive growth in expected demand is mainly due to the shift to e-mobility. Including not only cars but our complete transport network (Statista, 2021). Recent studies show that the production of an e-vehicle generates almost twice the amount of CO2 compared with the production of a standard diesel-powered car, mainly for the impact of batteries (Volkswagen, 2019). Though it may seem marginal when compared to emissions from our current fossil fuel consumption, battery pollution will become a significant environmental concern in the future.

With its DIY participatory and open approach, the DIYR project suggests possible directions to deal with the battery problem. It will offer a comprehensive guide with insights about the problems' cause and effect, together with detailed DIY instructions for salvaging and refurbishing used batteries. DIYR would as well base all its battery-driven products on second-life batteries and would encourage its proDusers to spread their use further on.

Becoming a counterpart to classical production methods of the industry, through DIY, new typologies, and a different approach to design and manufacturing emerges. While the concept of DIY defuses the manufacturing process of a product and, thereby, allows some of the components to be sourced locally and assembled by the creator (Bonvoisin, 2016). That sharpens awareness for sustainable consumption. DIYR also addresses transparent and traceable resource management as by encouraging proDusers to learn more about what they engage in. If in the industry some of the approaches of DIY, for example, design for maintainability containing simple assembly and disassembly of a product, only slightly were to be followed, this would have enormous positive consequences in terms of sustainability on the production

of goods (Go, et al. 2015). Accordingly, this project sets to generate new locally-oriented production perspectives, in which the user is encouraged and empowered to become a proDuser. Engaging with producing their own products and in the process coming in contact with local production possibilities and ecosystems. The voluntary pursuit of knowledge is serving here as a strong driving force, as further knowledge and skills are acquired through making and doing as well as from peers and experts.

Through the process of making, the personal attachment of the creator to the product arises, which generates more comprehension for the processes behind and culminates in care for materiality and the arising thing (Ingold, 2012). It merges production and usage where the user becomes responsible for the resources and produced goods. Pride, success, and learning value motivate and support the proDuser and culminate in the personal growth of the creator (Sennett, 2008).

DIYR products, thus, differ greatly from high-end electric products, but in terms of formal aesthetics and quality, they can compete and potentially exceed the latter, while at the same time offering maximal transparency, together with reparability and an optimized life expectancy potential. Furthermore, it incorporates the open and consolidating principles of Maker culture and fuses them with coherent logic and aesthetical values. DIYR seeks to form a new benchmark for Maker projects, where form, function, and overall logic are woven together into new typologies, aesthetics, and an aware production and use. Moreover, DIYR offers finished, thoughtfully designed open-source objects.

A rich and elaborated online open-platform would cater for both communicating the visual aspects of the products as well as the assembly instructions next to providing the necessary information - background and references to further develop one's understanding, knowledge, and skills.

The DIYR project aims at developing a growing family of DIY products, which through strong identity and distinct communication would form a new 'brand' of (DIY) electrical appliances. These can give impulses and become potential discussion pieces for the industry, reflecting on a multitude of perspectives and future possibilities. One of the objectives of DIYR is to become a brand, where money is no longer paramount, but knowledge, quality, sustainability, and awareness are. It aims to provoke and subversively appear as a commercial brand, on par with the other competitors, but raising contradiction and not selling any physical product but sharing content and an attitude. By stimulating self-construction and personal engagement with a scope of topics, it can serve as a valuable trigger for a paradigm shift. Thereby, it could potentially reach those who otherwise would not (aspire to) personally engage with such topics.

3.2 Design Process and principles

The DIYR design process starts with a critical questioning on what exists as products in the market and further redefines new principles for constructing them with a DIY logic. For each new product, an ad-hoc design process is followed, breaking the existing principles of how it is made and re-constructing it with a "DIYR" approach and DNA. It passes through a design process starting from "Doing It Ourselves" as designers to preparing "Do It Yourself" recipes for others.

Taking the Bluetooth loudspeaker as an example, key aspects in its development were:

- **Re-sorting the existing:** one of the initial activities of the project was dismantling a representative (wide) scope of existing conventional loudspeakers, stereos, and Bluetooth loudspeakers. This helped in gaining valuable insights into industry standards and logic for these devices, their structure, materials, components, and use.
- **Re-defining the content-container relationship:** based on the analysis of current industry standards and the above-mentioned specific investigation it became evident that once freed from industry standards and production logic, a complete revision in content - container relationship could take place and with it the potential to redefine and newly find product typologies and use patterns. Once freed from the industrial dogma of boxing, hiding, and masking, physical transparency, and openness prevailed, having as far as possible the content serving as container. As the resonating body of the loudspeaker (4mm corrugated cardboard sheet in its core) is regarded as a decorative surface and space for personalization and personal interaction. Furthermore, where only made possible the electronic components are left 'open' and visible and used in such a way that their function could be illustratively evident.

- **Research into technology:** being updated about new electronics and technologies is a crucial part of the whole process - it continues from the beginning until the end. Depending on available technologies or components, the design process can take a different leap that can change some main decisions about the structure of the product. This process depends on the commercial electronic producers and the industry. The design process feeds itself from the advancement of technology supplied to the industry, for instance, a microcontroller, although produced for a specific product in the market, could be integrated as a component in another DIYR product.
- **Searching for new aesthetics:** while working on the logic of the product, material experimentations of various sorts are done, trying out new combinations of materials, colors, patterns, and forms in the 3D-printed and other parts of the product. This stage goes in parallel with the re-defining of the content-container relationship since both can feed each other.
- **Re-thinking the making – DIY instructions:** a state-of-the-art study of visual instructions and relating visual storytelling was the base to the concept of the DIYR instruction. Favoring the freedom of 3D CAD environments and the precision of vector drawings, unlike most open platform instructions the DIYR recipes are not making use of photos but feature fully illustrated and annotated drawings with clear systemic logic and impactful visual language.

3.3 Future potential within the Fab Lab community

DIYR is a context-dependent research activity, starting from a pilot context – the BITZ city Fab Lab of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano – and aims at enlarging its field of action to other Fab Labs and partners of the project. The dialogue with active and potential proDusers will help the project to further develop solutions that are based on the real experience and perspectives of its target group/s. The project continuously generates new knowledge about the following research questions:

- How can design and designerly tools enable passive users to become active proDusers?
- How could design-driven artefacts serve as sustainable catalysts in the DIY and Maker Worlds?
- Could design-driven innovation give new sense/s to distributed manufacturing and revive the (old) dogma of Fab Labs as viable local production hubs?
- The form-follows-function dogma on all its values hardly exists currently in electronic artefacts, in what ways could DIY(R) electronics change that?

While answers to these questions would be formulated further on during the project, some new questions will emerge based on the debate that the project outcomes will lead to. Indeed, the project's goal differs from a mere problem-solving approach, rather it offers a new vision of alternative production possibilities that can raise questions for the industry, the maker's community, and consumers alike.

By having iterative cycles in the research process (Fig.3), the DIYR project aims at connecting to other Fab Labs to produce new outcomes (recipes for DIY electronic artefacts) that will be tested and validated by diverse target groups located in different places, based on the Fab Lab locations.

3.4 Target Groups and educational value

The project's main pilot study takes place at Fab Lab BITZ, which has over 800 members, ranging from teenagers to elderly citizens. This wide range of participants offers the possibility of interaction with diverse stakeholders getting involved in the project. Furthermore, the project foresees a knowledge transfer to other Fab Labs located in different cities [Milan (Polifactory), Munich (Fab Lab München), etc.]. While instructions and blueprints will move from one place to another, the production will happen locally in each Fab Lab setting. This will also involve different target groups that are determined by the local context.

Figure 3: Action research Spiral adapted from Action research cycle by Villari (2015)

Another possible direction to widen the target group is to involve younger participants that are already active or would like to be active in such topics of sustainability and/ or technology. Already, STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art & Math) education activities enable children and youth to come into immediate contact with electronics. While these activities are generally related to open-ended play activities there are no viable examples that go beyond prototyping and becoming a real-life usable object. The products made would further serve as discussion and communication pieces promoting the project and its values, enlarging the potential cycle of awareness to family, friends, and so on.

4 Reflections

With its sustainability-oriented blueprint based on true on-demand diffused manufacturing principles, with high proDuser involvement, the DIYR project offers a more sustainable and longer-lasting alternative to nowadays short-lived mass products, mass production, and mass consumption.

Opening the option for its future products to be based on 'second life batteries' directly retrieved by its users highlights another important sustainable aspect of the project. According to the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), finding a secondary use for batteries after their initial application is one of the most effective ways of prolonging their life while also increasing their value (Pesaran, 2021).

Through the 'doing' by 'ourselves' the project aims as well at reaching higher emotional value for its products and instigating a different relation to them. Thus, evoking a will to sustain them with more awareness and care, driven by one's emotional value rather than the plain economical one. This perspective shift could further lead to a more conscious manner of dealing with all that surrounds us - from products to resources or nature at large. Furthermore, by doing 'ourselves' we become more informed about the product, its function, its components, and its sourcing, thus repairing it when needed, becomes an integral part of the making. Repairing and the repair culture on all its positive values are here an integral part of the project's DNA and a key aspect in any sustainable product future scenario.

The project could potentially become a significant new tool for Fab Labs to illustrate their capabilities to both existing as well as potential new members. Especially those that might otherwise have not discovered the Fab Lab (i.e 'i want to have this, therefore I want to do this...'). In the Fab Lab context, DIYR products

aim to raise and strengthen certain discourses, awareness, and ways of making and doing that are scarcely there, especially from a sustainability and design perspective. Through design-driven thinking, Fab Labs can further develop as hubs for alternative production systems giving the user not only the power to produce an electronic product by her/ himself but also the responsibility for one's choices and awareness of environmental issues.

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